

MENTAL DISORDER, SUPERSTITION & SOCIETY

Ranjana Singh

Abstract

The aim of this paper is to assess the myths, beliefs, and perceptions about mental disorder and health seeking behaviour in general population and superstitions in the society. Also, this article attempts to show the importance of the concept of superstition in understanding a range of psychological problems. With this aim, this paper critically analyze several constructs that, without actually using the term "superstition," concern this phenomenon and its role in the development of mental disorders. This study focuses on social and psychological factors associated with superstitions. It sheds light upon the pros and cons for adherence with superstitious beliefs. The findings reveal that superstitious beliefs are widely spread and there are socio-learning pre dispositions which lie at backdrop of superstition. Superstition castes negative influences on psychological health of individuals. Over the entire article is worthy effort for articulated understanding of phenomenon of superstition and its associated factors which open horizons for the related and in depth enquiries. Most aspects of mental illness and psychological well-being are influenced by social factors (such as gender, social class, race and ethnicity, and household patterns) and social institutions (such as disability and social security systems, labor markets, and health care organizations). The capacity to cope effectively with growing number of persons with mental illness and/or dementia depend substantially on the social arrangements affecting family, work, income support and medical care.

Keywords: Mental illness, misconceptions, stigma, faith healer, health seeking behaviour, superstition, witch hunting

Introduction

Mental health is the ability to adjust oneself with the various stressful situations of the environment. A mentally healthy person lives a fuller, happier, harmonious & effective life. The essential dimension of mental health is clear from the definition from the definition of HEALTH in the WHO (World Health Organisation)

constitution: "Health is a state of complete physical, mental & social well being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity".

Mental Health is the foundation for well being & effective functioning for an individual and for a community. This core concept of mental health is consistent with its wide & varied interpretation across cultures.

Traces of superstitions can be detected in the fibers of every society. The prevalence of superstitious beliefs can be stretched from old primitive cultures in the form of paranormal, magical and superstitious activities to present modern days (Newport & Strausberg, 2001). Superstitions are present in different forms in our society, subject to unique set of cultural beliefs and ideals (Ouédraogo & Mullet, 2001). It is an extensively explored topic in psychological research. The significance of superstition beliefs and its impact on behaviors are wide spread, researches indicated that consumers exhibited superstitious beliefs as mental short cuts which impact upon their purchase behaviors (Carlson, Mowen, & Fang, 2009).

The effects of superstitious beliefs can be witnessed in debit in business in United States which shows loss of \$800 and \$900 million on 13th Friday every year 13th (Ng, Chong, & Du, 2010). Also numerous studies have found that road accidents raised extensively on Friday the 13th (Hughes, 2002; Lewis & Gallagher, 2001; Nayha, 2002). In Taiwan people pay 15 percent more than actual rate for product when it shows number 8 which perceived as lucky digit (Kramer & Block, 2008). Surprisingly in China the association of good luck with number eight can be witnessed; Beijing Olympic Games were held on 8/8/08 (Carlson et al., 2009).

Superstition: A Conceptual Framework

Superstitious beliefs is noticed in behaviors exhibited by individuals in different life situations hence an articulated concept of superstition is a necessary aspect. Superstition conceptualized as "Any thought or irrational act and illogical fear or dread of something mysterious and fantasy and a doubt or habit that its basis

is ignorance or fear, is called superstition." (Jahuda, 1371, p. 5). Other explanations included superstition as behaviors which are perceived to have controlling power for luck and other external forces but they lack operational clarity to perform certain acts (Foster, Weigand, & Baines (2006). Superstition referred as groundless beliefs with lack of justified rationale. In American Heritage Dictionary, concept of superstition cited by Kramer and Block (2008) as incongruence beliefs with are against natural phenomenon but overall considered as logical by the members of particular society. Giner- Sorolla in 1999, defined superstitious acts as superstitions are appraisals for behaviors which involve lack of careful cognitive functions.

Superstition as an attitude can be understood from affective, cognitive and behavioral aspects. The emotional aspects includes arrays of feelings that ranged from fear, apprehension, to joy and delight towards superstitious laden objects. The cognitive aspect encompasses conceptualization, assimilation and strategic planning of behavior and predicting future outcomes where as the behavioral component comprised of different rituals people engaged to avoid accidents or facilitate their desired outcomes for their own selves or their loved ones.

Mental Disorder

Mental and behavioural disorders are present at any point in time in about 10% of the adult population worldwide.

The burden of mental disorders is maximal in young adults, the most productive section of the population. Neuro Psychiatry conditions together account for 10.96% of the global burden of diseases as measured by disability – adjusted life years (DALYs). Projections were estimated that by the year 2020 neuro psychiatric conditions will account for 15% of the disabilities worldwide with unipolar depression alone accounting of 5.7% of DALYs, and will stand 2 nd in top 10 leading causes of disabilities.

The total economic costs of metal disorders are substantial in terms of gross national product (GNP) loss. In most countries, families

beer a significant proportion of these economic costs because of the absence of public funded comprehensive mental health service networks.

In the context of India situation is very different, there's no concept of mental disorder in our country's rural area. Lack of awareness regarding mental illness, it is connected to superstition, like, witchcraft (commonly known as 'Dayan Bisahi' in India). Especially referenced to the state of Jharkhand. In the state of Jharkhand, killings frequently happen due to assumed witchcraft. The role of society is also highly apprehensive.

The objective is to assess the myths, beliefs, and perceptions about mental disorders, and health seeking behaviours in general population and medical professionals of India.

In India, the prevalence of mental disorders ranges from 10 to 370 per thousand population in different parts of the country, the median conservation estimates of 65 per thousand population has been given by Gururaj etc. The rates are higher in females by approximately 20 -25% as for as causation of mental morbidity is concerned, there are many factors similar to any other world community, but delayed health seeking behaviour illiteracy, cultural and geographic distribution of people are special in India.

Access to adequate mental health care always falls short of both implicit and explicit in part by the fact that mental illness is still not well understood, often ignored.

In Gumla district of Jharkhand, frequently it is heard by the newspapers that all the members of a family were shot by the people of the same village in order to panchayat.

Large population of this district are tribal and there is too much illiteracy, unawareness and superstition among the people. If a person starts suffering from any kind of mental illness, the villagers call a person who is commonly known as 'Ojha' or 'Guni', whom people think that they'll treat the illness, but in reality, the person is

actually a 'Quack'. Villagers think that 'Dayan Bisahi' is responsible for any sort of illness or death. In some scenarios when the illness starts getting worsen, the villagers murder the person who is suffering along with his/her family members. These activities are a big challenge for humanity and a big threat for the society.

Mental Health Acts:

The **Mental Health** Act was drafted by parliament in 1987, and came into effect in all states & union territories of India in April 1993. It is an "Act to consolidate & amend the law relating to the treatment & care of mentally ill people, to make better provisions with respect to their property & affairs and for matters connected there with or incidental thereto."

The **World Federation for Mental Health** has declared 10 th October as the International Mental Health Day. It is a day for global mental health education, awareness & advocacy.

Superstition

Superstitions are long-held beliefs that appear to be rooted in coincidence or cultural tradition rather than logic or facts.

Superstitions are often connected to pagan beliefs or religious practices that were widespread in the past.

Our ancestors didn't come up with superstitions because they were more ignorant naive than we are, but because they lacked many concrete ways to influence the survival outcomes of their lives, superstitions offered a way to feel more in control, the same way they do now. That's why highly educated, sophisticated people still believe in certain superstitions.

Most superstitions are fun and harmless, whether you sincerely believe in them or not. But some superstitions can play into mental health conditions, such as obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD).

Real Life Example of Superstition of Gumla district of Jharkhand, India:

In 2019, a boy died in Gumla by drowning in a well, the family members of the boy were unaware that the boy was in well, and was drowning. Once the dead body of the boy was discovered by the boy's family, the family members called a Quack to get the boy back to life. The quack asked the family members for some grains & food, after getting all the stuff he needed, the quack told the family to completely cover the boy's dead body with salt, and keep it for 48 hours. The family did everything the quack told. After 48 hours the boy was still dead, and the family had to bury the dead body.

Some Other Common Superstitions found in Indian society:

- Crows: Crows are scavenger birds and many believe they can sense death before it happens. For this reason, some people believe seeing a lone crow means calamity is eminent.
- Black Cats: Poor black cats. They are blamed just for being black (no racist joke here). It's a popular belief in the west too that, if a black cat crosses your path, it's a bad omen.
- 13: Number 13 is just considered unlucky.

SOCIETY: Superstitions are common phenomenon in human society especially in Asian cultures. Superstitions & beliefs can have a negative impact on the social well being of people in society because they are highly associated with financial risk-taking and gambling behaviours.

There is very worst situation of mentally ill woman in society. When they are healthy, they serve the whole family from day to night, but when they get mentally disturbed by the exploitation and torture by the family members gradually, the situation of the woman becomes very worst then their so called '*own*' family does not support properly, and sometimes they even say that "*it's her drama*", and then the send the woman to her parent's house for treatment. If any

survey on this topic is done, then we'll find that no husband's family member will see for treatment of his wife or their daughter-in-law, only her own parents, brother or sister will be there for her treatment. These situations are still in our society because of unawareness of Psychology.

Witch Hunting In India

India is a land where the women are treated as symbol or are consider as a token of their community, family, caste and all other diverse divisions.

Witch Hunting In Past Few Years:

As per the report of National Crime Record Bureau (NCRB) 2008, in the state of Jharkhand of India there were 52 witchcraft related murder, in Haryana around 26 of witch hunting were reported, whereas in Andhra Pradesh and Orissa 23 cases were reported, in Madhya Pradesh 17, in Chhattisgarh 15, in Maharashtra 11 and in west Bengal and Meghalaya 4 and 3 respectively. According to NCRB, instances of witch hunting has increased when compared to previous year data.

Also, as per Human Right committee report in last 15 years approximately 2,500 women were killed in name of witch hunting. Previously it was seen that witch hunting is only associated to women, but in 2013 in Orissa police reported a case where a boy was killed as he was accused of practicing witchcraft. And in Assam where a girl was raped in name of witch hunting in 2011.

In 2015 and 2016 the crime against women and witchcraft is 32% and 27% which violates the right of women.

LEGISLATIVE APPROACH TO WITCH HUNTING

- There is no specific and particular national level legislation that penalizes witch hunting hence the provision under the Indian penal code 1860 can be used as an alternative for the victim.

- The different section invoked in such cases are sec. 302 which charge for murder, sec 307 attempt for murder, sec 376 which penalizes for rape and sec 354 which deals with outraging a women's modesty.

Apart from the provision under Indian penal code different states have come up with different legislation to tackle the problem of witch hunting

- Jharkhand followed it and established "Anti witchcraft Act" in 2001 to protect women from inhuman treatment as well to provide victim legal recourse to abuse. Basically section 3, 4, 5 and 6 of concerned Act talk about the punishment which will be granted if any one identifies someone as witch, tries to cure the witch any damages caused to them.
- Bihar though being most backward was the first state in India to pass a law against witch hunting in the year 1999, which was named "prevention of witch practices act".

Poor Implementation of Prevalent Laws:

- State which have enacted laws and not effective as it lacks of national legislation.
- Also due to the quantum of punishment which is granted to the accused is lesser than a gravity of the crime they have committed, up to 1 year with a fine of Rs. 1000.

Social Issues in Areas Affected With Superstitious Practices

- Well planned activity.
- Means to grab property and control.
- Whole community is engaged.
- Poor and inaccessible area affected with extremists.
- No comprehensive awareness and education program.

Findings and Discussion

Social isolation has long been known as a key trigger of mental illness, while supportive relationships with friends, family & neighbours are beneficial to the mental health of individuals and the population. Other forms of social interactions such as, volunteering is also known to boost well being.

Mental health is fundamental to the health and productivity of every culture and serves as the foundation of productive families, communities, and society as a whole. Major mental illnesses like schizophrenia, depression, bipolar disorder, and panic disorders occur worldwide and to all racial and cultural groups.

There's a strong association between culture and mental health stigmas, several surveys and studies show that differences in stigma exist between various groups all though research offers few explanations to why these differences exist.

- The cultural perception of people with mental illness as being more dangerous, as compared to the perceptions held by another race.
- Reluctance to marry or employ someone with a mental illness.
- A call for separation from those with mental illnesses, even though research shows interaction usually reduces stigmatization.
- Reluctance to engage in treatment out of fears that their race would elicit unfair conduct on the part of healthcare workers.
- Suppressed communication between the health care professionals and patients regarding the state of an individual's mental health status.
- Reluctance to share information or concerns about one's

mental health status with friends, co-workers, or family members.

- The perspective that mental illness reflects poorly on the entire family.

Many mental health experts consider mental illness to be the product of complex interactions between biological, psychological, cultural, and social factors. The contribution of each of these factors varies by disorder.

Ethnic, racial, and cultural minorities experience a special social and economic environment of inequality that increases their risk for exposure to racism and discrimination, violence, and poverty. There is a strong association between poverty and mental illness, according to the World Health Organization (WHO), with common mental disorders occurring about twice as often among poor people as in the rich. The highest rates of mental illness often occur in those with the lowest levels of education and in the unemployed. In particular, individuals with the lowest socioeconomic status have eight times the relative risk for schizophrenia than those in the top socioeconomic class.

Part of the reason for this cyclic relationship is that people living in poverty have fewer opportunities for education or employment, suffer exposure to harsh living conditions, have little access to good health care, and lack the financial resources necessary to maintain basic standards of living. These stressful conditions can contribute to the development of a mental disorder that can prevent these individuals from working or increase their risk for suffering discrimination in the workplace. Without a job, people are unable to pay for the effective treatment they need.

Conclusion

It can be concluded from this study, that the myths and misconceptions are significantly more prevalent in rural areas than urban areas and among medical professionals, and the people need to be communicated to change their behaviour, and develop a

positive attitude towards mental disorders, so that health seeking behaviour can improve.

References

- Faiza, A. (2018). Social and Psychological factors for Superstition: A Brief Literature Review. *International Journal of Advance Study and Research Work*, 1(5), 81.
- Foster, D. J., Weigand, D. A., & Baines, D. (2006). The effect of removing superstitious behavior and introducing a pre-performance routine on basketball free-throw performance. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, 18(2), 167-171.
- Kramer, T., & Block, L. (2008). Conscious and nonconscious components of superstitious beliefs in judgment and decision making. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 34(6), 783-793.
- Ng, T., Chong, T., & Du, X. (2010). The value of superstitions. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 31(3), 293-309.
- Ouédraogo, A., & Mullet, E. (2001). Prediction of performance among West African male farmers: Natural and supernatural factors. *International Journal of Psychology*, 36(1), 32-41.
- Treusch, A. H., Vergin, K. L., Finlay, L. A., Donatz, M. G., Burton, R. M., Carlson, C. A., & Giovannoni, S. J. (2009). Seasonality and vertical structure of microbial communities in an ocean gyre. *The ISME journal*, 3(10), 1148-1163.
- Wiseman, R., & Watt, C. (2004). Measuring superstitious belief: Why lucky charms matter. *Personality and individual differences*, 37(8), 1533-1541.

